

D8.3: Final Dissemination Report

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents a final report on dissemination activities throughout the three years of the 3D-ICONS project.

The mission of the 3D-ICONS project has been to raise awareness amongst archaeology and architecture content holders of the positive conditions for making 3D content available to Europeana, and to give a persuasive demonstration of best practices to promote use of the project's results by the wider community.

The target audience for the project's dissemination strategy include:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- External stakeholders: Organisations with an interest in 3D digitisation including Europeana, cultural heritage institutions, academic institutions, commercial enterprises and others;
- The Research Community;
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP and Horizon 2020 programmes: directors, project officers and related projects.

Section 2 of this report introduces the aims and objectives of the dissemination work package.

Section 3 describes the dissemination plan, the development of the project website and project portal, the dissemination materials that have been prepared, work to build the stakeholder community, and dissemination of news and information via the project newsletter and social networking channels. Monitoring statistics for each of these activities are provided.

Section 4 describes the project's participation in conferences and events, including the three international workshops that were organised by the project, involvement in training workshops, clustering activities with other projects such as the ARIADNE and DARIAH research infrastructures, and publications by project partners.

Section 5 monitors the success indicators that were identified by the project in its description of work and dissemination strategy. Monitoring of the project's dissemination activity during the three years of the project showed that the targets set at the start of the project have been met and in most cases have been exceeded:

- More than three international events have been organised
- Partners have participated in more than 35 international conferences giving more than 62 presentations; and have participated in around 30 national events. Four summer schools have been organised by partners.
- 45 articles have been published in conference proceedings and academic journals (a few of this number will be published in 2015).
- The project website has received more than 23,460 visits from 17,830 visitors in 157 countries
- Project news and the newsletter are being read by more than 300 people
- The project has established external partner agreements with six organisations and informal collaboration agreements with twelve projects active in 3D digitization and twelve associations.

2 Introduction

WP8 (dissemination) has been active from the beginning of the project. All of the project partners have taken part in the work package and have played a role in disseminating news about the project's activities.

The initial activities for the Work Package were to establish the project's dissemination plan to guide activities during the first year. During the first three months the project's website was established together with an initial set of dissemination materials. These materials have been regularly updated and extended throughout the project.

Building the stakeholder "database" has been an important activity. In these days, where so much communication takes place online through social networking sites such as Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook, the priority has been to build a following for the project on the networks. This has been achieved by sharing project news and information about events, along with news and information from related initiatives. A database of contacts who registered on the project to receive copies of the project newsletter has also been built up.

In addition to online communications, the project has organised three workshops (one in each year of the project) at international conferences to present the project's results. Partners have been very active in participating in international and national conferences and events, and in organising summer schools. A large number of presentations have been given by partners to conference delegates, articles written and papers published.

All of this activity is reflected in the large numbers of visitors from across the world to the project website and in the monitoring statistics which are presented in the following sections of this report.

3 Dissemination planning

The main aim of the project's dissemination strategy has been to raise awareness about the 3D ICONS project and 3D digitisation amongst:

- Colleagues within the partner organisations such as senior managers, researchers with an interest in 3D but not active within the project itself.
- External organisations with an interest in creating and using 3D including Europeana, cultural heritage institutions, academic institutions, commercial enterprises and others.
- The 3D research community,
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP and Horizon 2020 programme: directors, project officers and related projects funded by the programme.

The dissemination strategy was prepared during the first six months of the project and was updated at month 24. The objectives included:

- Identifying channels of communication and opportunities for networking activities.
- Building the stakeholder contact database and the network of followers in Twitter, Facebook, Linked in and Slideshare, and other social media channels.
- Clustering with related projects.
- Sharing and exchanging news about project events and activities, and other relevant news.
- Maintaining and developing the Project website and portal.
- Presenting the project at national and international events, and in workshops organised by the project.
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials.

3.1 Project website

The 3D ICONS website (<http://www.3dicons-project.eu/>) was established to offer information about the project and its partners, and to present the results of the project. Reports, presentations and papers by project partners have been made available on the website along with news, information about events, a gallery, guidelines and a series of case studies.

Our objective throughout the project has been is to increase the traffic on the website by disseminating news about new publications, news stories, case studies and newsletters via email marketing and the social networks.

The website was set up by MDR and is now hosted and maintained by 2Culture Associates for the project.

The screenshot shows the 3D ICONS website homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following links: About, News, Events, Resources, Portal, Guidelines & Case Studies, Gallery, and Community. Below the navigation bar, there are three large image tiles: a 3D model of a castle, a 3D model of a landscape with circular features, and a person using a 3D scanner. The main content area is divided into three columns: 'About 3D Icons' with a 'Read More' button, 'Latest News' with a 'See All' button, and 'Events' with a 'See All' button. On the right side, there is a 'Tweets' section with a 'Follow' button, displaying tweets from @digicultEU, @IntarchEditor, and @welovehistory.

Google Analytics have been used to track and analyse traffic to the 3D ICONS website. Here is a summary of the traffic during the period from 1st February 2012 to 31st January 2015:

- Visits to the website were reported from 157 countries
- 23,461 sessions were recorded from 1 February 2012 to 31st January 2015 from 17,830 visitors.
- 76% were new visitors with 24% returning visitors

- 66,769 pages have been viewed since the start of the project with an average of 2.85 pages per session and a 62.54% bounce rate.

3D ICONS website: visits by country

Analysis of visits to the website show a gradual increase in traffic with a peak in visits in the week of 8 September 2013 following the CIPA Symposium in Strasbourg.

Website visits by week

Website visits by month

Top referrals

The top 20 referrals to the website during the period were:

The top referral Facebook (7.7% or 437 sessions). An article in El País Andalucía on “El patrimonio ibero se expande en 3D” which was published on 14th September 2013 resulted in 316 sessions (5.57% of all referrals):

http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/09/05/andalucia/1378398178_073401.html

Eleven of the top referrals are project partners' websites.

The CARARE project website has also been an important referral leading to 154 sessions (2.72% of referrals) largely to the CARARE 2.0 metadata schema documentation, news and other resources.

Top content

The top viewed content on the website was:

- home page: www.3dicons-project.eu, 18,460 views
- about, 4,552 views
- resources, 4,469 views
- news, 4,303 views
- community, 2,483 views
- events, 2,049 views
- gallery, 1,842 views
- consortium page, 1,091 views
- user login, 647 views

Analysis of the top viewed content shows that while most visitors are going to the home page and the pages about the consortium but importantly resources, news, community, events and the gallery are also attracting visitors.

The 3D ICONS Case Studies, which were published in late autumn 2014 several of which were tweeted during December 2014 and January 2015 attracted several hundred views during this period.

3.2 Implementing the project portal

The 3D-ICONS Portal <http://3dicons.ipet.gr/> was implemented for the project by CETI.

The objective of the portal is to demonstrate the functionalities and advantages for displaying and browsing digital cultural content via a map-based user interface. The 3D-ICONS Portal consists of four main components:

- Map Engine
- Search Component
- Metadata Presentation
- Responsive Design
- Route Planning

The pilot data consists of all 3D models data ingested to Europeana and all objects from the 3D-ICONS Project partners. The portal is a prototype.

Functional specifications

- Mapping every object to the geographical view
- Responsive design of the web application to be user friendly for different devices such as desktop PC, laptop, tablet, smartphones.
- Search component to find specific digital and physical objects and implemented with checkboxes selection for increased usability. The search types required:
 - Search by Keyword
 - Search by Country
 - Search by Type of object
 - Search by Size of object
 - Search by Time Spans
- Smartphone: usage of compass to display the nearest object to the user's current position.
- Display enriched information for every object according to the metadata content.
- Display country and town based object with mouse left click.
- A hyperlink direct to Europeana for every object on the application.
- Simple and friendly user interface.

Technical specifications:

- Use of Open Source Platform
- Usa of Europeana API
- Use of technological components in Europeana ICT as much as possible
- Parsing and post processing of metadata

3.2.1 Data

The pilot data consists of all the 3D ICONS project content plus other 3D models data ingested to Europeana from other providers.

The content has been processed as follows:

- 3D-ICONS Project: metadata of the objects has been geoparsed and ingested to the portal.
- Europeana API: Data has been parsed through the API and then processed for ingestion into the 3D-ICONS Portal.

3.2.2 Map engine

The goal of the map component is to answer to the main question: “What is where?”

Every 3D model from Europeana and the 3D ICONS Project is geo-located for display on the map. When the user clicks on an object a modal box appears to display information about the object itself and any related objects. When the user left-clicks in the map a modal box displays the objects in that country or town. Functions include:

- GIS functions to zoom to all, zoom-in, zoom-out, pan.
- Changing of the base layer between Map, Satellite, Hybrid.
- Showing the thumbnails of objects.
- Detailed description of an object

Implementation

The Map Engine is an Internet application developed and implemented using:

- Google Map API V3
- Joomla! 3
- IIS 7 with .NET framework 3.5, MySQL, PHP on server side.

3.2.3 Search component

The main goal of the search component is to provide an easy way for users to find specific heritage assets according to their interests.

The search component is implemented with checkboxes for ease of selection. There are seven options:

- Search by Keyword
- Search by Country
- Search by Type
- Search by Organisation
- Search by Size
- Search by Date

In addition there is a search by radius option on the map.

Displaying Results (Pagination with dropdown selector)

Implementation

The search component is implemented using:

- XML Processing
- Checkboxes query
- Google Map API V3
- Joomla! 3
- IIS 7 with .NET framework 3.5, MySQL, PHP on server side.

3.2.4 Presentation of Heritage Assets

The metadata related to an object is shown when the user clicks on a heritage asset in the map.

Rotunda (3D)

Ultralow resolution 3D model

Metadata	Information
Appellation	Rotunda (3D)
Address	Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece
Coordinates (Lat, Lon)	(40.633296, 22.952845) Click to view it on Google Maps
See it on Europeana	
Link	Link
Landing Page	Landing Page

Heritage Asset
Digital Resources
Paradata
Related Objects

The Rotunda was built at the northeastern part of the city, close to the east city walls. Its location was previously an uninhabited, sparsely built area, which was added to the city during the 3rd century fortification. The building is located on the axis of the road that was leading through the Arch of Galerius to the royal palace to the south. It was actually connected to this Arch through a monumental colonnaded way and consequently to the palace. It was travelers in the 18th and 19th centuries that gave the monument its common name, i.e. Rotunda, due to its circular plan. The monument has a rich history of more than 15 centuries, during which its function and shape changed. These phases, that are the theme of an ongoing scientific debate, will be briefly presented here. The first Roman phase of the monument began when it was initially built in the Late Roman period, in the late 3rd or early 4th century AD. The Rotunda's initial arrangement was like that of the Pantheon in Rome. It had a circular plan, with a diameter of 24,5 meters and 6,3 meters thick walls. It was constructed with bands of brick and rubble made from local greenish-white stones, with mortar binding. Eight niches were opened in the walls approximately 5,0 meters in depth, while colonnaded screens were dividing the niches from the central space. The southern niche opened into a propylon. There was a row of eight large windows above these big ground-floor niches, while nine smaller lunette windows also pierced the upper part of the structure. The building was roofed with a dome and was located inside a precinct. The dome today consists of two distinctly different zones, the lower one with a regular hemispheric curvature, while the upper one with a slightly steeper curvature. This difference is explained as different construction periods of the parts of dome. Indeed, researchers state that the dome may have originally remained unfinished or it may have needed repair after an earthquake. As for the founder of the building, the most widespread scientific

Heritage Asset Display

Heritage Asset – Related Objects

Implementation

- XML Parsing
- Checkboxes query
- Using Google Map API V3
- Using Joomla! 3
- Using IIS 7 with .NET framework 3.5, MySQL, PHP on server side.

3.2.5 Responsive Design

The web application is accessible and adapted for various browsers and different types of devices following the principles of responsive design; a web design approach aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing experience—easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling—across a wide range of devices (from mobile phones to desktop computer monitors).

In addition, when a user accesses the application with a mobile device it automatically displays all objects near to the current position.

1368*768 (15 inches)

1024*600 (10 inches)

320*568 (Smartphone)

320*568 (Smartphone)

Implementation

- CSS Media Query
- Using Google Map API V3
- Using Joomla! 3
- Using IIS 7 with .NET framework 3.5, MySQL, PHP on server side.

3.2.6 Portal – Google Analytics

Google Analytics has been used to track and analyse traffic to the 3D ICONS portal (<http://3dicons.ipet.gr/>). Here is a summary of the traffic to the site during the period from 1st September 2014 and 25 January 2015:

- 1520 sessions
- 350 Users
- 3,946 Page views, with an average of 2.59 pages per session
- Average visit duration of 5 minutes 20 seconds
- Bounce rate: 55.81%
- 77.35% returning visitors

Location

Sep 1, 2014 - Jan 25, 2015

 All Sessions
100.00%

Map Overlay

Summary

Country	Acquisition			Behavior			Conversions		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages / Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate	Goal Completions	Goal Value
	1,523 % of Total: 100.00% (1,523)	22.65% Avg for View: 22.65% (0.00%)	345 % of Total: 100.00% (345)	55.81% Avg for View: 55.81% (0.00%)	2.59 Avg for View: 2.59 (0.00%)	00:05:20 Avg for View: 00:05:20 (0.00%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)	\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (\$0.00)
1. Greece	529 (34.73%)	17.58%	93 (26.96%)	36.48%	4.11	00:10:14	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. France	293 (19.24%)	23.21%	68 (19.71%)	61.77%	1.88	00:03:10	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. Italy	283 (18.58%)	24.38%	69 (20.00%)	57.24%	1.86	00:03:02	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. United Kingdom	210 (13.79%)	5.24%	11 (3.19%)	75.71%	1.62	00:02:15	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. Russia	57 (3.74%)	1.75%	1 (0.29%)	96.49%	1.04	00:00:01	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. United States	24 (1.58%)	91.67%	22 (6.38%)	83.33%	1.21	00:01:06	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)

Analysis of the statistics by country reflects the distribution of the project partners with the largest numbers of visits coming from Greece, France, Italy and the UK.

The portal statistics show that the top browsers and operating systems used by visitors were:

- Firefox 55.8%
- Chrome 32.24%
- Safari 9.26%
- Internet Explorer 1.77%
- Android Browser 0.39%
- Opera 0.26%

3.3 Project dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials was prepared for the project by MDR Partners. This set of materials has been extended throughout the project; some elements of the set are described in more details below. The base materials that have been made available include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners
- Project fact sheet and postcard
- Project poster(s)
- 3D ICONS Essentials PowerPoint presentation.
- Templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.

3.3.1 Logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher for MDR Partners.

3.3.2 Video

A project show reel was produced by Discovery incorporating contributions of videos of 3D digitisation projects from several partners.

The video was prepared for the exhibition at Digital Heritage 2013 and has now been uploaded to YouTube and incorporated into the project website on: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/Community>.

3.3.3 Poster

3D-ICONS is digitising iconic monuments and buildings, many from World Heritage sites, to bring around 3,000 3D models to Europeana and its users.

The project will establish a processing pipeline from digitisation, post-processing, metadata and final output formats.

3D-ICONS is using the CARARE2 Metadata Schema which is specifically designed for archaeology and 3D models.

info@3dicons-project.eu

3D ICONS is funded by the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme

www.3dicons-project.eu

3.3.4 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Project materials such as reports, presentations, promotional material and publications acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement such as: "This project is partially funded under the ICT Policy Support Programme (ICT PSP) as part of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme by the European Community"

Together with a link to the ICT PSP website: http://ec.europa.eu/ict_psp and the programme logos where appropriate.

3.4 Building the stakeholder community

The dissemination work package involves all partners in the project consortium with partners in 10 countries and a broad network of contacts.

All partners have contributed to the project's dissemination activities helping to develop project materials, identifying events, sharing news and presenting the project's activities to stakeholders. CISA, with MDR and more recently its sub-contractor 2Culture Associates, has had strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners.

3.4.1 Clustering with other projects

3D ICONS identified a number of projects who are active within its field. These include projects within the Europeana network as well as projects with a research focus.

3D ICONS has collaborated with these projects to exchange news and other activities where opportunities have arisen. The projects which have been identified include:

- CARARE (<http://www.carare.eu>: Europeana, archaeology)
- 3D COFORM (<http://www.3d-coform.eu/>: researchers)
- V-MUST (<http://www.v-must.net/>: researchers and creative SMEs)
- Scottish Ten (<http://www.scottishten.org/>: researchers and creative SMEs)
- Partage Plus (<http://www.partage-plus.eu/>: Europeana, museums)
- Europeana (stakeholder community: cultural institutions)
- ARIADNE (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>: researchers, archaeology)
- DARIAH-EU (<https://www.dariah.eu/> : researchers)
- Athena Plus Project (<http://www.athenaplus.eu/> : Europeana, museums)
- Europeana Creative (<http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-creative>: Europeana, museums)
- meSch project (<http://mesch-project.eu/>: researchers)
- CyArk (CyArk: heritage)

A recent example of collaboration with another project in this cluster is the uploading of a small number of 3D models produced by 3D ICONS to the new Visual Media Service developed by ISTI-CNR as part of ARIADNE: <http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>. This data is helping ARIADNE to test the new service.

3.4.2 Networks

There are a number of networks that have an interest in 3D digitisation, these include conferences, groups and various associations. Individual partners are members of many of these networks and many have mailing lists and a presence on Twitter, providing opportunities to share and exchange news and information. Some of the networks are:

- Europeana Network (<http://pro.europeana.eu/network>: membership association)
- Europeana Tech (<http://pro.europeana.eu/web/network/europeana-tech>: membership association)
- Digital Heritage (<http://www.digitalheritage2013.org/>: conference)
- Museums and the Web (<http://www.museumsandtheweb.com/>: conference)
- ICOMOS (<http://www.icomos.org/en/>: NGO and membership association)
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (<http://caa-international.org/>: conference)
- European Association of Archaeologists (<http://e-a-a.org/>: membership association)
- Irish Institute of Surveyors (<http://www.irish-surveyors.ie/>: membership association)
- Aerial Archaeology Research Group (<http://www.univie.ac.at/aarg/>: membership association)
- International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (<http://www.isprs.org/>: membership association)
- European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories (<http://www.earsel.org/welcome.html>: membership association)
- Network TechnoHeritage: Red de Ciencia y Tecnología para la Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural (Science and Technology for conservation of Cultural Heritage) (<http://www.technoheritage.es/>: research network)

3.4.3 Stakeholder database

3D ICONS has gradually built up a contact database by encouraging registrations on the project website, subscriptions to the project newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project's Facebook and LinkedIn groups, and to disseminate news and information via these channels.

Targets were set to increase the project's following on the social networks during 2014. The targets were:

- Twitter increase from 150 to 300 followers
- Facebook increase from 82 to 150 members
- LinkedIn (CARARE group) 597 to 650 members

3.5 Disseminating news and information

Our objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events and project activities. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below.

3.5.1 Project newsletter

KMKG has been responsible for coordinating the production of regular issues of the project newsletter with contributions from all partners. The newsletters have been disseminated directly to registered stakeholders via the Mailchimp service and indirectly to mailing lists by sending out notices to followers on the social networks.

The newsletter is also published online and copies are available from:

<http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Newsletter>.

The editorial strategy has been to create articles talking about 3D ICONS related topics including:

- project achievements
- events attended by the project Consortium
- partner profiles
- dynamic articles describing activities such as field work
- news from projects active in same area as 3D ICONS

Latest news on 3D scanning of world heritage

Newsletter #6

Welcome to the sixth issue of the 3D-ICONS newsletter! 3D-ICONS is a project funded under the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme and is using 3D techniques to digitise UNESCO World Heritage Sites and to provide content to Europeana.

In this issue we *highlight results* of the project so far, as they appear in Europeana and on the partner websites. Plus, as usual, updates on conferences and events

Follow 3D-ICONS on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook

You can find 3D-ICONS colleagues on LinkedIn [here](#).

Facebook: Login and go to [3D-Icons](#).

3D-ICONS brings tweets on 3D from a wide variety of sources.

Below what we thought was of interest over the last days. Interested in more?

Follow [@3DICONS](#)

3D-ICONS workshop in Paestum, October 30th 2014

At the 17th Mediterranean Exchange of Archaeological Tourism, the 3D-ICONS project will stage a [workshop](#), presenting the aims and results of the project.

At the conference, the first issue of the 3D-ICONS Guidelines will be released.

Photogrammetry summer school in Romania

The International Summer School Photogrammetry applied to Cultural Heritage took place in Jurilovca, Romania, 21 -27 September 2014. Read more [here](#)

[Friend on Facebook](#)

[Follow on Twitter](#)

['Approaches to Archaeological Landscapes - Tools, Methodology and Case Studies'](#), which will be held from 22nd-23rd October 2014 in Bucharest, Romania.

[EuroMed 2014](#)
 Mon 3 Nov 12:00 - Sat 8 Nov 15:30
 The 5th EUROMED conference brings together researchers, policy makers, professionals, fellows and practitioners to explore some of the more pressing issues concerning Cultural Heritage today.

[AR&OA Biennial](#)
 Thu 13 Nov 09:18 - Sun 16 Nov 16:30, the 9th Biennial of Heritage Restoration and Management is a meeting point and discussion forum for professionals and institutions in the fields of protection, curatorship, conservation, restoration and

Newsletter distribution

The project dissemination plan set a target of 300 readers of the project newsletter by month 36. The newsletter is distributed directly via the Mailchimp service to subscribers (people who have registered their interest in receiving the newsletter on the project website) and indirectly via notices on Twitter and the mailing lists. To analyse the readership of the

newsletter and articles published within it, we need to look at the statistics gathered by both the Mailchimp service and in Google analytics for the website.

The Mailchimp service provides tools which allows us to analyse the direct distribution of the newsletter. The statistics Issue 6 of the newsletter was sent to 161 registered recipients, the analytics provided by Mailchimp show that the newsletter had:

- An opening rate of 42.3% (the industry average is 23.3%)
- A click rate of 20% (the industry average is 2.8%)

The top links clicked by readers were:

- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Summer-school-Romania>
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/3D-Icons-conference-Paestum>
- http://3dicons.gamsau.archi.fr/europeana/index.php?VARdr=TRIANON_SSN343_3D_1
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/About/Gallery>
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/New-video2>

Top locations by opens

The indirect distribution can be interpreted using the website statistics show that the newsletter and news items are consistently amongst the top viewed content. For example:

- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News> had 4,306 page views and was the 4th most viewed content page on the project website.
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Museum-digitisation-in-Milan> had 292 page views with an average of 2.32 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Digitization-of-Saint-Michel-de-Cuxa> had 252 page views with an average of 2.18 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Abbadia-Castle> had 239 page views with an average of 2.10 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Newsletter/Issue-3> had 180 page views with an average of 1.37 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Metadata-for-3D-objects> had 185 page views with an average of 2.43 minutes spent on the page

- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Poulnabrone-Scanning-Ireland> had 177 page views with an average of 2.13 minutes spent on the page

Analysis of the statistics suggest that readership of <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News> and the newsletter is on target, with analysis of the website statistics showing that recipients of the newsletter and notices on Twitter and Facebook are interested and are following follow the links to read the full news story published on the project website.

Monitoring

	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
Newsletter	Direct subscribers: 161	40

3.5.2 Twitter

MDR set up a Twitter account for the 3D ICONS project (@3DICONs). The account is managed by KMKG and 2Culture Associates for the project who both tweet about the project and retweet news of interest

The target audience for the Twitter account has been people who have a direct interest in 3D digitization including researchers, professionals, Europeana and the digital libraries community, cultural heritage and industry end-user organisations, publishers, online hosts, academic institutions and SMEs.

The objectives have been to:

- Keep key followers informed of 3D ICONS activities (progress made, publications, upcoming events etc.)
- Inform followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to 3D digitisation of the Cultural Heritage.
- Informing followers about new content on the 3D ICONS website, Facebook and LinkedIn.
- Informing followers about upcoming conferences, workshops, info days, etc.

3D ICONS has followed people who are related to the target audience and professionally involved in 3D digitisation. We do not follow people whose tweets are of a personal nature and periodically review and 'unfollow' the less useful tweeters.

At the start of the project the project aim was to Tweet at least once a fortnight. This rate of tweeting was not sufficient to build a following and so since the start of 2014 the project has aimed to Tweet or reTweet at least five days a week.

The 3D ICONS account replies to specific tweets directed at @3DICONs (asking questions or feedback about the project).

Monitoring

	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
Twitter twitter.com/#!/3dicons	Tweets: 638 Following: 217 Followers: 318 Retweets: 263 Favourited tweets: 63 tweets (107 times) Mentions: 159	+ 376 + 166

Analysis of 3D ICONS using Twitonomy shows that the increase in activity on Twitter from June 2013 onwards. 48% of the projects tweets have contained links to further information.

Aror

the

Users most retweeted

3D ICONS has been mentioned 159 times and has had 135 retweets by 73 Twitter users in the period between 20/03/2012 and 28/01/2015.

The most influential followers (Twitter users with the most followers) were:

- Build3D printer (70,183 followers)
- GiusMellio (11,985 followers)
- AndaluciaTuCult (9,135 followers)
- BAMstraCult (3,972 followers)
- Erfgoednieuws (3,392 followers)
- Artmedieval (2,864 followers)
- Arkeografia (2,858 followers)
- fet_eu (2,750 followers)
- opticalsurvey (2,339 followers)
- digicultEU (2,258 followers)

The potential reach of 3D ICONS twitter account was estimated at 221,457 twitter users (the total aggregated number of users who follow the people who mentioned @3DICONs-project)

3.5.3 LinkedIn

KMKG set up a group for 3D ICONS on LinkedIn. During 2013 this group was merged with the existing (and much larger group) established by the CARARE project.

The group can be found at: http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=2792030&trk=anet Ug_hm

By 28th January 2015, the group had 636 members. Postings to the group include notices from project partners, notices from group members about conferences and events, and questions (or requests for information) from members of the group about technologies and other areas of interest.

Monitoring

Monitoring shows that membership of the group continues to grow.

	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
<p>Linkedin http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=2792030&trk=anet_ug_hm</p>	Members: 636	+38

3.5.4 YouTube

A YouTube channel was established for the project and six videos have been uploaded and were embedded in news stories on the 3D ICONS project website. They received 565 views.

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel page for '3DIconsProject'. The channel has 7 subscribers. The 'Uploads' section displays six videos:

- 3D ICONS Film Reel**: 14:58, 138 views • 1 year ago
- 3D Digitization of the Abbey of Saint-Michel de Cuxa, ...**: 0:57, 151 views • 2 years ago
- Gallarus Oratory Laser Scan**: 0:51, 64 views • 2 years ago
- Drombeg Stone Circle Laser Scan**: 0:50, 55 views • 2 years ago
- Cahergal Stone Fort Laser Scan**: 0:51, 53 views • 2 years ago
- Recording the equinox at Puente Tablas**: 3:25, 104 views • 2 years ago

	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
YouTube http://www.youtube.com/user/3DIconsProject?feature=watch	Subscribers: 7 Videos: 6 Video views: 565	+5 + 308 views

In addition to the 3D ICONS channel, several partners established YouTube channels for their own activity in the project. For example:

Discovery Programme 3D ICONS (<https://www.youtube.com/user/DP3DICONS/>) - DISCOVERY has uploaded 30 videos since October 2014. These have been viewed 547 times.

MultimediaRCathena (<https://www.youtube.com/user/MultimediaRCathena>) - the Xanthi division of the Athena Research Centre has uploaded 21 videos to its YouTube channel since December 2012. These have received 8,167 views.

3.5.5 FaceBook

A Facebook group has been established for the project at:
<http://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/>.

The FaceBook group is widely used by members to share news about digitisation projects, new 3D models, videos and other resources. Many partners also post news about 3D ICONS to their own/organisational FaceBook groups/

Monitoring

Network	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
Facebook http://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/	Members: 126	+44 members

3.5.6 Slideshare

A Slideshare account was set up for the project to share publications and presentations. By 28th January 2015, the project had shared 19 documents and 30 presentations on Slideshare.

The presentations are embedded into the project website using the Slideshare viewer and can also be found via: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/Resources/Presentations>

The screenshot shows the 3D ICONS website interface. At the top, there is a header with the 3D ICONS logo and navigation links: About, News, Events, Resources (highlighted), Portal, Guidelines & Case Studies, Gallery, and Community. Below the header, a breadcrumb trail reads 'Home > Resources > Presentations'. The main content area is titled 'Presentations' and includes the text 'Presentations by members of the project team'. A section for the year '2014' lists two presentations:

- Anthony Corns, XVIII Borsa Mediteranea del Turismo Archeologico conference in Paestum**: Includes a link to '3D ICONS Guidelines and Case Studies' and a 'Download file' button.
- Gabriele Guidi, Sara Gonizzi Barsanti and Laura Loredana Micoli at the 3D ICONS workshop at the XVII Borsò Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico conference in Paestum**: Includes a 'Download file' button.

A sidebar on the right contains a 'Presentations' section with a 'Share' button and other resource links.

Project reports, deliverables and paper pre-prints have also been uploaded to Slideshare. By 28 January 2015 there had been 11,837 views of 3D ICONS presentations and documents on Slideshare.

The top viewed content on was:

- **2289 views** - Web visualization of complex reality-based 3D models with Nubes, a pre-print of Jiménez Fernández-Palacios, B., Remondino, F., Lombardo, J., Stefani, C. and L. De Luca: "Web visualization of complex reality-based 3D models with Nubes". Digital Heritage 2013 Int. Congress, IEEE Proceedings.

- **925 views** - Iberian sculptures from the Museum of Jaen using 3D scanning and photography, presentation by Anna Sánchez given during the 3D ICONS workshop at Digital Heritage 2013
-
- **379 views** - 3D-ICONS: World Heritage Sites for Europeana Making Complex 3D Models Available to Everyone paper by Andrea D'Andrea, Franco Niccolucci, Sheena Bassett and Kate Fernie presented at VSMM 2012

Monitoring

Network	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2014
Slideshare http://www.slideshare.net/3dicons	Followers: 12 SlideShares: 49 Views: 11,837	+11 +44 + 11039

3.6 Press conferences and media reporting

Press notices and press release are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: Newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

In March 2012, Daniel Pletinckx of Visual Dimension took part in an event to mark the official opening of the tourist season in the province of East Flanders, Zottegem, Belgium:
http://www.radiomfm.be/plugins/p2_news/printarticle.php?p2_articleid=2237

Press conference to launch 3D-ICONS project in Spain was held at the University of Jaén on the 21st May 2012: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/CAAI-launches-3D-ICONS>

An interview about the 3D Icons Project was given by Tudor Martin to the *Radio România Cultural* radio channel on the 11th September 2012. The interview was broadcast on *Radio România Internațional*, a radio channel dedicated to Romanians living abroad.

Radio Nacional de España interviewing Alberto Sánchez

- Diario Ideal (newspaper)
- Diario EL PAIS (newspaper)
- La Razón (newspaper)
- Cadena SER (radio channel) (interviewed Arturo Ruiz)
- Radio Nacional de España (interviewed Alberto Sánchez)

A press conference was held about 3D-ICONS progress in Spain on July 11, 2013. The 3D models of Cerrillo Blanco, Porcuna, Jaen were presented. See: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/CAAI-presents-first-results>.

The media who attended or published information were:

- Canal Sur Televisión (TV channel)
- Onda Jaén Televisión (TV channel)
- Ondaluz Televisión (TV channel)
- Viva Jaén (newspaper)
- Diario Jaén (newspaper)

Special report of Jaen newspaper about 3D-ICONS and the Iberians. Section Campus. <https://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/>

Official Irish launch of 3D-ICONS project at the Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, Ireland 18th April 2012: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/New-3D-Project> Booth at VSMM2012 Milan, Italy, 2-5 September 2012, showing a general overview on the project, organized by Polimi. 3D Icons mentioned in the “Dissemination Partners” list: http://www.vsmm2012.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=13&Itemid=124

There was a full page news item in *Archaeology Ireland* magazine, Winter Issue 2013

3D-ICONS: the Discovery Programme participates in a major European 3D documentation project

The Discovery Programme, which celebrated its twentieth anniversary last year, has always striven to be at the forefront of technological developments in archaeology. From the use of topographical survey techniques in early projects such as Tara to the recording of archaeological landscapes using photogrammetry in north Roscommon, new approaches and technologies have been a core element of their research projects. One such technological advance to have a major impact on archaeology has been 3D recording and modelling of sites and monuments using laser scanning technology. An excellent example of this, the work at Douth and Knocknabreena by Dr David Strange-Walker and UCD, was published in the Autumn 2012 edition of *Archaeology Ireland*.

The Discovery Programme has been using laser scanners since 2006 for a wide variety of applications: recording excavation surfaces, upstanding monuments, remains of ruined buildings, earthworks, architectural details, carved rock art and artefacts. As a consequence of this broad experience and in-house expertise, the Discovery Programme together with sixteen partner institutions across Europe secured EU Commission funding through the ICT Policy Support Programme for a three-year pilot project. Entitled 3D-ICONS, the project started on 1 February 2012 and is focused on the 3D documentation of UNESCO World Heritage monuments and other monuments of outstanding value at European level. Its core aim is to involve organisations with recognised expertise in 3D data acquisition and modelling to establish a full production pipeline. This will cover all aspects of a 3D digitisation project, from planning and obtaining permissions, selection of methods and tools, data acquisition, post-processing, publication of content on-line and metadata capture to making the content available through Europeana: a portal to millions of books, paintings, films, museum objects and archival records that have been digitised throughout Europe. More details of the project can be found on the project website, <http://3dicons-project.eu/en/>.

To be a partner in this project is an exciting challenge for the Discovery Programme and they are involved in all aspects of 3D-ICONS, from project coordination and management to making content available for dissemination. Their major contribution, however, is to provide 3D content to represent Ireland. Based largely on the UNESCO World Heritage List (and tentative list), this will include a selection of complex archaeological landscapes, detailed structural models of buildings, carved rock art and artefacts. Sites

proposed so far include some obvious choices—Bri na Bóinne, Skellig Michael, western stone forts (An Gríanan Alligh, Cahergal, Dúcachair, Dún Aonghusa, Dún Eochla, Staigue), royal sites (Dún Ailinne, Hill of Tara, Navan Fort, Rathcroghan), Clonmacnoise and Glendalough—and some less obvious but nevertheless interesting and representative of Ireland, such as the Derry city walls, Drombeg stone circle, Gallanus oratory and Poulnabrone portal tomb. This is only a pilot project, so hopefully in time a more comprehensive and inclusive list of Ireland's iconic sites can be considered for 3D digital documentation.

Beyond the defined activities of 3D-ICONS, the 3D documentation of such high-profile monuments should have a significant impact in Ireland. The models generated provide a valuable resource for the conservation and monitoring of monuments. They provide an accurate and detailed baseline from which future change through processes of decay, erosion or even vandalism can be measured and quantified. 3D models provide an engaging resource in education, providing the potential for interactivity and participation in the learning environment. Detailed models and reconstructions of archaeological sites can be used to provide remote access and understanding to distant visitors or those physically unable to visit sites. Used imaginatively, 3D models can help to market the cultural heritage of Ireland, encouraging visitors whilst raising the profile of technological advances—both with significant potential benefits for the economy.

3D-ICONS provides an excellent collaborative opportunity to draw on international expertise from across Europe to define a strategy for documenting and distributing 3D models of heritage sites. For Ireland to be represented is an acknowledgement of the encouragement and commitment to technical excellence given to the Discovery Programme by the Heritage Council. ■

Left: A perspective view of the intensity-value 3D point-cloud looking through the entrance of the formidable walls of Stalgaue stone fort.

Top: A perspective view of the intensity-value 3D point-cloud of the oratory at Gallarus.

Archaeology Ireland Winter 2012

Following work by **DISC** with partners in Derry connected to the 400th anniversary of the city walls, the activities and the 3D ICONS project were reported in several national newspapers in Ireland and also in the UK's Sunday Times.

- <http://www.derryjournal.com/news/local-news/derry-s-walls-go-digital-1-4948848>
- <http://www.londonderrysentinel.co.uk/news/digital-scanning-of-largest-monument-for-400th-birthday-1-4953236>
- <http://www.belfasttelegraph.co.uk/news/local-national/northern-ireland/see-derrys-walls-in-a-new-dimension-famous-landmark-being-mapped-in-3d-29167859.html>
- A ¾ page article by DISC in the Sunday Times national newspaper describing the 3D-Icons Project has provided national coverage for the project and Europeana in the UK.
- <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/In-the-news>

Report on 3D-ICONS project and CETIs digitisation activities in Greek newspaper 'Δημοκρατία Βορείου Ελλάδος' (Democracy Northern Greece), Issue 241(647) Monday 18 February 2013, pp 36.

Visual Dimension started a blog about its work on visualisation of the Benedictine abbey at Ename: <https://enameabbey.wordpress.com/>

Arturo Ruiz, CAAI, 3D model presentation and press conference about the Sanctuary of Puente Tablas (Jaén, Spain).

DISC interview with SketchFab (<http://www.sketchfab.com/>) to be posted on their website in February 2015. The interview describes the wide array of users the 3D-ICONS project and the digitisation process for cultural heritage.

The Discovery Programme is planning to publically launch the www.3dicons.ie web site which contains all 3d content, images and videos of all the monuments surveyed during the project, on 17th March 2015 (St Patrick's Day). This will be carried out with support from two government departments in Ireland (Dept Office of Public Works & Dept of Arts Heritage and Gaeltacht).

Anthony Corns of the Discovery Programme was interviewed by Sketchfab for its Sketchtalk blog. The interview is published here: <http://blog.sketchfab.com/post/110056824389/sketchtalk-the-discovery-programme-is-preserving>

The image shows a screenshot of a blog post on the Sketchfab website. The page header includes the Sketchfab logo and navigation links for 'EXPLORE', 'COMMUNITY', and 'BLOG'. A search bar is also present. The main content area features a large blue title: 'SketchTalk: The Discovery Programme is Preserving Ireland's Past'. Below the title is a photograph of a person in a yellow safety vest standing on a ladder, positioned next to a large, ancient stone structure (a dolmen) in an outdoor setting. The person appears to be operating a 3D scanner or camera mounted on a tripod. Below the photograph, there is a short paragraph of text: 'It you're interested in 3D scanning and Cultural Heritage, then you've probably noticed the Discovery Programme on Sketchfab. They have been very actively publishing new models and I was interested to learn more about their efforts. Today I talk to Anthony Corns who is their Technology Manager.'

4 Conferences, events and other dissemination activities

4.1 Conferences and events

3D ICONS has been presented at a large number of conferences and events since the project began (see Appendix 1 for the full list).

4.2 3D ICONS international workshop - 2012

CISA organised the 3D ICONS workshop within the framework of the VAST2012 International Congress in Brighton on November 21st 2012 with support from STARC and several partners. The initiative was attended by 15 people from different countries.

After a short introduction given by Sheena Bassett (MDR) about the objectives of the project, the Workshop focused on metadata for 3D Models with the contributions of Andrea D'Andrea (CISA) and Kate Fernie (MDR). They were followed by Mike Spearman (CMC), who illustrated the preliminary report on IPR and business model. Finally, Marco Callieri (ISTI-CNR) gave a contribution about the 3D technologies for Cultural Heritage. The participants asked many questions and were genuinely engaged with the subject. It was also interesting to hear and to share about their practical experiences.

Programme

Franco Niccolucci, CISA - Welcome and presentation

Sheena Bassett, MDR - A brief introduction to 3D ICONS

Kate Fernie, MDR – Metadata, the CARARE aggregation service and 3D ICONS

Andrea D'Andrea, CISA - Combining the outcomes of CARARE and 3DCOFORM to capture in 3D, store, manage and retrieve the digital Monuments of Europe at best

Mike Spearman, CMC – Rights and IPR issues

Marco Callieri, ISTI-CNR – 3D ICONS digitisation planning

Andrea D'Andrea presenting

Workshop participants

4.3 3D ICONS international workshop - 2013

DISC organised the “Exploring the 3D-Icons Project on Thursday October 31, 2013. The workshop was hosted at the Digital heritage International Congress 2013 in the spectacular surroundings of the newly built Museum of Civilisations from Europe and the Mediterranean (MuCEM) in Marseille, France. The workshop was designed to introduce the 3D-ICONS

Project to the wider research community and explore the digitisation pipeline developed as part of the project. This pipeline exploits and integrates existing tools and methods that enable the capture, modelling description and publication of 3D cultural heritage content on the web. The project pipeline themes of capture, model, describe and publish also informed the structure for the workshop sessions to provide a narrative structure for the audience.

Participants @ 3D ICONS workshop

DISC case study @ 3D ICONS workshop

Several of the partners contributed to the workshop providing case studies of digitisation work in progress, on metadata capture, quality control, use and re-use of 3D models. (CISA, MDR, DISC, FBK, MAP, MNIR, VisDim, UJA-CAAI, CYI-STARC and Polimi). The workshop was attended by 29 participants.

News story: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/DigitalHeritage2013>

4.4 3D ICONS final project event - 2014

The final project event was organised by CISA and was held during the Borsa Mediterranea Del Turismo Archeologico in Paestum on 30th October 2014.

The Borsa Mediterranea is an annual event held at Paestum in Italy near the Greco-Roman site archaeological site. It combines presentations and talks on archaeology and tourism with an exhibition promoting regional goods, tourism and services for archaeology offered by companies and institutions such as the University of Florence's VAST Lab. Participants at the event may also visit the archaeological park and the museum for free.

The event (now in its 17th year) attracts a large international audience of professionals and students involved in archaeology and tourism, and also members of the general public (who mainly participate at the weekend).

3D-ICONS hosted a 3 hour workshop on Thursday 30th October, organised by CISA with Italian and English speakers. The room was packed and nearly everyone stayed for the whole 3 hours. The majority of the participants were students or young professionals who were very interested in 3D modelling and its application in archaeology.

Andrea D'Andrea

Andrea D'Andrea, CISA, introduced the project and three 3D-ICONS partners gave presentations on different aspects of the project:

Anthony Corns of the Discovery Programme provided an overview of the Guidelines and Case Studies (which had just been published) and the processing pipeline developed by the project. A series of case studies were introduced.

Alberto Sanchez of CAAI at the University of Jaen addressed how the creation of 3D models met the need for archaeological documentation and research.

The final project presentation was given by Gabriele Guidi of POLIMI who described how they collected the metadata and completed the scanning for the objects from the Archaeological Museum in Milan.

Carlo Resigno of the Università degli Studi di Napoli "L'Orientale" then gave a presentation on disappearing architecture.

The closing speech was by Prof. Pesando, the President of CISA at the Università degli Studi di Napoli "L'Orientale".

Alberto Sanchez

The workshop flyer and presentations by project partners are available in Slideshare and on the project website at: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/Events/3DICONSBMTA2014>.

4.5 Other events

Reshaping History, 30 October 2012, Naples. Andrea D'Andrea presented 3D-ICONS at the opening of this exhibition, organised by 3D-COFORM. The Archaeological Superintendent of Naples and Pompeii and Alderman for Culture and Tourism of the municipality of Naples were present. The exhibition was at the Museo Archeologico Nazionale in Naples.

Spar Point Group interview by Anestis Koutsoudis of CETI. The interview was published online on the 5th of September 2012: <http://www.sparpointgroup.com/Blogs/Continental-View/Interview--Dr-Anestis-Koutsoudis---At-the-cutting-edge-of-Greek-3D/>.

18th International Conference on Virtual Systems and Multimedia (www.vsmm2012.org) organized by POLIMI in Milan, Italy in September 2012. A 3D ICONS information booth was set up to show the project to the conference attendees; booth rental gave the right to add the project logo and link on the VSMM2012 supporter page.

Built Heritage 2013 in Milan, 18-20 November 2013 (<http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/>). Franco Niccolucci chaired a session on “3D survey, modeling and monitoring” at which several partners presented papers.

NTUA has disseminated about Europeana and the 3D ICONS project through its collaboration at national level in Greece including with the ‘Reviving the Ancient Agora in Athens’ project of the American School of Classical Studies in Athens and the ‘Digitisation and Promotion of the Archaeological Findings in Greece’ project of the Archaeological Society at Athens.

Summer school on “3D Surveying and Modelling in Cultural Heritage”

FBK and the University of Salerno organised a week-long summer school which took place on June 16-22, 2013 in Paestum (Italy).

News story: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/News-from-Paestum>

Participants at the Paestum summer school

Photogrammetry workshop in Romania

MNIR presented the 3D ICONS project at the first 3D photogrammetry workshop in Romania on the 22nd August 2013. The workshop was organised by the Romanian National History Museum and F64 (a leader in the Romanian photo market).

News story: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/MNIR-workshop>

4.5.1 Events with other projects

Presentation of the project within the EU Marie Curie funded Radio-Past Colloquium: *Non-destructive approaches to complex archaeological sites in Europe: a round-up*, Approximate audience 80 people by the Discovery Programme.

3D ICONS at DARIAH/IANUS IPR Workshop, Berlin

The 3D-ICONS Project was invited to talk about their experience with IPR for 3D Models at an IPR workshop jointly organised by the IANUS and DARIAH-DE projects in Berlin and hosted by the German Archaeological Institute in September 2013. MDR presented on the IPR situation with regard to 3D models with D7.2 providing the basis for the presentation.

News story: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/3D-ICONS-at-DARIAH-IANUS-IPR-Workshop-in-Berlin>

ARIADNE 3D and Visualisation Special Interest Group

Several partners took part in a meeting of the ARIADNE research infrastructure's 3D and Visualisation Special Interest group, which was organised on behalf of ARIADNE by CNR and held in Pisa on 7-8 October 2013.

News story: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/3D-special-interest-group>

Project collaboration workshop, Museums and the Web Florence, February 2014

3D ICONS is organising a project collaboration workshop with Creative CH and V-Must.net the day before Museums and Web Florence 2014. The aim of the workshop is to share experience and results and to discuss future plans.

<http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/Events/Workshop>

4.6 Publications

Partners have produced 43 articles which have been published in conference proceedings and academic journals (a small number of these articles are currently in press). The full list of partners' publications is provided in Appendix 2

Articles have been accepted by a wide range of publications including:

- Digital Heritage 2013, International Congress, IEEE Proceedings
- Journal of Archaeological Science, 40 (2013)
- Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, XXIV International CIPA Symposium
- Built Heritage 2013 proceedings
- Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer Vision (Oral), ICCV, Sydney, Australia
- R. Klein and P. Santos (eds.) EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage
- International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era
- L., M. Boriani, and G. Guidi (eds), Built Heritage: Monitoring Conservation Management Research for Development 2015
- ISPRS Annual Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing Spatial Inf. Sci., 2014
- Journal of Cultural Heritage, Volume 15, issue 1, January-February 2014
- M.A. Rogerio-Candeleria (ed), 2014, Science, Technology and Cultural Heritage, 2014
- The Photogrammetric Record, Volume 29, Issue 146, 2014
- Proceedings of CHNT 2014. (in press)
- Built Heritage: Monitoring Conservation Management', Springer International Publishing. (In press).

5 Monitoring and evaluation

The project description of work and then the dissemination plan identified a series of success indicators that we have used to monitor and evaluate the project's dissemination activity.

5.1 Success indicators

Three performance monitoring indicators were identified in the description of work:

- Papers published and other presentations
- Attendance of external experts to project's events/presentations
- Liaisons & agreements with institutions / consortia not involved in project's activities (formal and informal)

The project dissemination plan added:

- Number of international events held
- Number of presentations at relevant conferences
- Project website: number of visitors to website
- Number of 3D ICONS connected social networks and the number of members
- Newsletter: Number of readers

Targets

Description		Target Month 12	Target Month 24	Target Month 36	Actual month 36
Papers published and other presentations	No.	10	20	30	45
Attendance of external experts to project's events/presentations	No.	50	100	150	340 *estimated based on an average of 10 participants at 34 separate events.
Liaisons and agreements (formal and informal)	No	10	20	30	30
International events held	No.	1	2	3	4
Presentations at international events	No.	10	12	15	62
Project website	Visitors	7,000	10,000	15,000	17,830
3D ICONS connected social networks	No.	2	3	4	20
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300	+300 of which 161 direct + twitter & mailing lists

5.1.1 Papers published

The description of work set a relatively modest target of 30 project related publications by month 36. With 45 publications in conference proceedings and academic journals, the partners have excelled.

5.1.2 Attendance of external experts to project's events/presentations

The description of work set a target of 300 external experts attending project events/presentations by M36. This information is difficult to capture. Based on the fact that partners have given 62 presentations at some 34 international events, and participated in a further 30 national events, and that these events were well attended. We estimated the attendance to be 340.

5.1.3 Liaisons and agreements

The Description of Work set a target for the number of formal and informal liaisons and agreements with institutions or consortia not involved with the project. The target of 30 such liaisons by month 36 was set. Currently the project has signed, external partner agreements with:

<http://www.uniss.it/youniss/> - ARSLAB at the University of Sassari based in Sardinia, contacted the project as a result of CYI-STARC modelling the Holy Well of St Cristina in Sardinia and are interested in the digitisation pipeline. (Signed)

<http://archive.cyark.org> – contacted the project as they are keen to expose their 3D models through Europeana. (Signed)

<http://www.groma20.com/> - who contacted the project via Facebook and has offered some very interesting content from Spain (Merida) which it is keen to make accessible via Europeana. (Signed)

<http://www.dainst.org/en/> - contacted the project to learn more about the CARARE2 metadata schema for documenting 3D models produced by DAI's different departments and locations. DAI sees visibility of its content in Europeana as an added bonus.

<http://vast-lab.org/home-en/> - CISA has enabled VAST-lab (part of PIN in Prato) to make some of its 3D models available to users of Europeana.

There is a partnership agreement in place between Polimi and the Archaeological Museum of Milan.

In addition to these formal agreements, we have established informal liaisons with 12 projects and 12 other networks (see section 3.4 above).

All 3D ICONS partners have signed Data Exchange Agreements with Europeana.

5.1.4 International events held

The project planned to hold an international workshop during each year of the project. By the end of month 36, project partners had organised the 3 planned workshops (at VAST 2012 and Digital Heritage 2013) and several additional events. Partners took part in an international workshop held during EuroMed 2012 and had delivered 6 training schools (Cyprus, Paestrum (2013 and 2014), Pontignano and Romania (2013 and 2014)).

5.1.5 Presentations at international conferences

The dissemination plan set a target of delivering 15 presentations at international conferences by month 36. This target has been exceeded with more than 43 presentations being given on the project or work being carried out in the framework of the project at 34 separate conferences.

5.1.6 Project Website

The dissemination plan set a target of 15,000 visitors to the website by month 36. With more than 23,460 visits from 17,830 visitors in 157 countries to the website by the end of January 2015, this target has been exceeded.

5.1.7 Social networks

The dissemination plan proposed that 3D ICONS should establish a presence on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Slideshare and YouTube but did not set targets for numbers of followers.

The initial dissemination plan set a target of 4 connected social networks by month 36. Amongst others we are following (and are followed by) these networks in Twitter:

- Digital Heritage
- CyArk
- Smithsonian 3D
- V-MUST
- MeSch Project
- Ariadne Network
- Partarge Plus
- Scottish Ten
- Europeana
- Europeana Tech
- digicultEU
- ISPRS

In addition the project is followed by these Twitter users (who also represent networks):

- Build3D printer (70,183 followers)
- GiusMellio (11,985 followers)
- AndaluciaTuCult (9,135 followers)
- BAMstraCult (3,972 followers)
- Erfgoednieuws (3,392 followers)
- Artmedieval (2,864 followers)
- Arkeografia (2,858 followers)
- fet_eu (2,750 followers)
- opticalsurvey (2,339 followers)

5.1.8 Newsletter distribution

The dissemination plan set a target of 300 readers of the project newsletter by month 36. By the end of the project 161 individuals had registered on the website to receive direct copies of the project newsletter. Distribution of the newsletter to mailing lists and via the social networks widened the readership beyond this group. The web statistics captured for individual news stories suggest that the target of 300 readers was met and exceeded.

6 Conclusion

This dissemination report presents our dissemination activities for the whole of the 3D ICONS project.

In the first year of the project dissemination activities focussed on raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts, and establishing the basic set of dissemination materials. In year two, dissemination activities focussed on presenting digitisation and other work in progress and project results, and on developing and extending the network of contacts. The focus in year three has been on presenting the project results such as the guidelines and case studies, and on publishing content on Europeana and in the project portal.

Monitoring of dissemination activity shows that the project partners have met and exceeding the dissemination targets that were set at the start of the project. It is pleasing to note the worldwide interest in the project's digitisation and other activities by the stakeholder community.

The 3D-ICONS project has been a "trail blazer" for the production and publication of 3D content for Europeana. Partners have explored new opportunities for publication such as ISTI-CNR's 3D-HOP and SketchFab, illustrating the possibilities for others creating 3D content for cultural heritage sites and institutions. The project is in discussion with Europeana about a 3D exhibition to promote the recent addition of around 4,000 new 3D models into the Europeana portal.

After the project has ended, the partners will continue to promote 3D-ICONS and the processing pipeline through conferences, in publications and via their own dissemination channels with many having active social media accounts as well as academic capital in the project. We envisage that the Facebook and LinkedIn groups established by the project will continue to be active in discussing new developments in 3D technologies.

The 3D-ICONS Portal will continue provide a showcase for the content, including the 3D models, provided by the project to Europeana. The 3D-ICONS website will continue to offer a source of relevant technical resources and case studies for developers and related projects, such as the ARIADNE infrastructure.

7 References

- [1] Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW
- [2] Deliverable 8.1, “Initial Dissemination Plan”
- [3] Deliverable 8.2 "Interim dissemination Plan"

Appendix I: Conferences and Events

The full list of conferences and events that project partners have participated in since the start of the project

Date	Event	Link
9-11 May 2012	EVA Florence, Florence, Italy Presentation and paper (CISA and MDR)	http://www.evaflorence.it/
13-15 June 2012	Europeana Plenary, Leuven Distributing postcards and networking (MDR)	http://pro.europeana.eu/web/leuven-2012
2-7 July 2012	3D Visualisation for the study and management of complex archaeological sites, summer school, Carnuntum, Austria Presentation (VisDim)	http://www2.radiopast.eu/wp-content/uploads/program-1.pdf
25 Aug – 1 Sept 2012	ISPRS Congress, Melbourne, Australia Presentation (FBK)	http://www.isprs.org/
29 Aug – 1 Sept 2012	CultureTECH, Derry/Londonderry, UK Presentation (DISC)	
29 Oct – 3 Nov 2012	EuroMed 2012 Conference, Limassol, Cyprus (FBK, MDR, CNRS)	http://www.euromed2012.eu/
2-5 Sept 2012	VSM2012, Milan, Italy (CISA, MDR, Polimi, FBK, CNRS, VisDim)	http://www.vsm2012.org/
25 Sept 2012	Presentations at KOREC Surveying Roadshow in Cork, Ireland (DISC)	
2 Oct 2012	Presentations at KOREC Surveying Roadshow in Belfast, UK (DISC)	
30 Oct 2012	Opening of “Reshaping history exhibition” at the Museo Archeologico Nazionale, Naples Presentation (CISA)	
21 Nov 2012	VAST 2012, Brighton UK – 3D ICONS workshop (CISA, MDR, CNR ISTI, CMC)	http://www.vast2012.org/
11 Dec 2012	Presentation to ICOMOS Ireland at the Royal Society of Antiquities Ireland (DISC)	
16 Jan 2013	Radio-Past Colloquium, Ghent, Belgium Presentation (DISC, VisDim)	http://www2.radiopast.eu/?page_id=2332

21 Feb 2013	VISIGRAPP 2013, International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications, Barcelona, Spain, (invited speech, ISTI-CNR)	http://www.visigrapp.org/?y=2013
9 Apr 2013	Laval Virtual 2014, Laval, France (Keynote, ISTI-CNR)	http://www.laval-virtual.org/en/
11 Apr 2013	Eurographics 2014, Strasbourg, France (Keynote, ISTI-CNR)	http://eg2014.unistra.fr/
13 Apr 2013	Rathcroghan Archaeological Conference 2013, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.rathcroghanconference.com/
May 2013	“Aggregating and promoting Visual cultural content”, Presentation at the annual meeting of the Union of Archaeologists, Plaka, Athens, Greece (NTUA)	
15 May 2013	Korec Technology Day 2013, Maynooth, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	
15 May 2013	EVA Florence, Prato workshop, Paper on new technologies (CMD)	http://www.evaflorence.it/
20 May 2013	Presentation of first project results to a general public audience and media including Radio România Cultural (MNIR)	
27-30 May 2013	Coordination and organisation of Virtual Heritage School 2013, The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus (CYI-STARC org, contribs. by CNR-ITABC, CNR-ISTI, POLIMI)	http://www.v-must.net/schoolscyprus-virtual-heritage-school-2013
28 May 2013	Korec Technology Day 2013, Belfast, UK, Presentation (DISC)	
29 May 2013	Patrimonium International Symposium, Alba Iulia, presentation (MNIR)	
30 May 2013	Round the World Symposium, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://kuleinstitute.wordpress.com/2013/05/
14-16 June 2013	Opening the past 2013, Pisa, Italy, Presentation (CISA)	http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/?page_id=1739

16-22 June 2013	Summer school on 3D surveying and modelling, Paestum, Italy (FBK org., POLIMI contrib.)	http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/News-from-Paestum
19 Jun 2013	24th Eurographics Symposium on Rendering, Zaragoza, Spain (Keynote, ISTI-CNR)	http://egsr2013.unizar.es/
27-8 June 2013	Cultural Heritage, Creative Tools and Archives Workshop, Copenhagen, Denmark, Presentation (MNIR)	
1-3 July 2013	International conference on digital signal processing (DSP'13), Santorini, Greece Presentation (NTUA)	http://dsp2013.dspconferences.org/
5 July 2013	Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past, University of York, UK, Poster (DISC)	http://www.york.ac.uk/digital-heritage/events/cdh-2013/
17 July 2013	Hill of Tara Annual Summer Lectures, Meath, Ireland (DISC)	
22 Aug 2013	Photogrammetry workshop, Romania (MNIR)	http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/MNIR-workshop
24 Aug 2013	Heritage Week 2013, Royal Society of Ireland (DISC)	http://www.discoveryprogramme.ie/news-a-events/news/218-dprsai-heritage-week-event-this-saturday-24-august.html
30 Aug 2013	3D Agora meeting Tervuren, Belgium, Presentation Networking (KMKG, VisDim)	http://agora3d.africamuseum.be/
1-2 Sept 2013	IANUS-DARIAH IPR workshop, Berlin, Germany (MDR)	https://de.dariah.eu/en/methoden-workshops
2-6 Sept 2013	CIPA Symposium, Strasbourg, France (FBK, POLIMI, CNRS)	http://cipa.icomos.org/
20-26 Sept 2013	Summer school "Drones applied to Cultural Heritage and Archaeology", Pontignano, Italy (FBK, CNRS, CNR)	http://www.v-must.net/activities/international-summer-school-drones-applied-cultural-heritage-and-archaeology
23 Sept 2013	TD 1201: Colour and Space in Cultural Heritage (COSCH), London, UK (presentation ISTI-CNR)	http://www.cosch.info/web/guest/home
26 Sept 2013	Aerial Archaeology Research Group (AARG) Conference, Amersfoort, Netherlands, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.decars.nl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=124&Itemid=76&lang=en

10 Oct 2013	eChallenges e-2013 Conference, Dublin, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.echallenges.org/e2013/
16-18 Oct 2013	3D-Doc. in Archaeology & Monument Preservation, held at LWL Industrial Museum, Dortmund, Germany (MNIR)	http://www.denkmaeler3.de/English/index-en.html
24 Oct 2013	European Walled Towns Symposium, Derry, UK, Presentation (DISC)	http://walls400.com/symposium/
24 Oct 2013	Scientific Support for Growth & Jobs: Cultural and Creative Industries Brussels, Belgium, posters and presentation (CYI-STARC)	http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/jrc/index.cfm?id=1410&obj_id=4700&dt_code=EVN&lang=en
28 Oct - 01 Nov 2013	Digital Heritage International Congress 2013, Marseille, France, Presentations and project workshop (CNRS conf org, DISC workshop org, contribs by CNR, CYI-STARC, FBK, POLIMI, VisDim, UJA-CAAI, MDR) networking (KMKG)	http://www.digitalheritage2013.org/
13 Nov 2013	SPAR Europe Conference, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.sparpointgroup.com/Europe/
18 - 30 Nov 2013	Built Heritage 2013 – Monitoring Conservation Management, Milan, Italy, Presentation (CISA, CYI-STARC, POLIMI)	http://bh2013.polimi.it/
27-29 Nov 2013	Virtual Retrospect 2013, Bordeaux, France (contrib by Archeotransfert)	http://archeovision.cnrs.fr/spip.php?rubrique41
2 Dec 2013	Europeana plenary meeting, Networking (CISA, MDR, KMKG)	
3-6 Dec 2013	International Conference on Computer Vision, ICCV, Sydney, Australia Paper (NTUA)	http://www.iccv2013.org/
19 Dec 2013	National Conference on Computer Vision, Pattern Recognition, Image Processing and Graphics (NCVPRIPG) 2013 organized by the Indian Institute of Technology, Jodhpur, India (Keynote, ISTI-CNR)	http://www.iitj.ac.in/ncvpripg/
16 Jan 2014	U3A Scotland, Paper on Scara Brae Survey (CMC)	

07 Apr 2014	Journées de l'association Nationales des Animateurs de l'Architecture et du Patrimoine	National event http://archeovision.cnrs.fr/IMG/pdf/laval_avr14.pdf
22-25 Apr 2014	Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA 2014), paper, CYI-STARC	http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/
18 Jun 2014	Journée Museohub "Numeriser restituer etudier transmettre le patrimoine", Bavay. (Presentation, Archeotransfert)	National event http://pictanovo.com/agenda/-museohub-2-numeriserrestitueretudiertransmettre-le-patrimoine-18-06-2014-142
23-5 Jun 2014	ISPRS Technical Commission V Symposium, 3D ICONS workshop (presentations FBK, CNRS-MAP, MNIR, Polimi, DISC, CETI)	http://isprs-commission5.fbk.eu/
27 Jun 2014	The Second International Congress on Science and Technology for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage. Seville, Spain. (presentation, CAAI)	http://www.technoheritage.es/Sevilla.html
26 Aug 2014	Heritage Week Public presentation and live scanning demonstration at Glendalough Monastic Site. (DISC)	National event http://www.heritageweek.ie/
5-12 Jul 2014	CIPA Summer school, Cultural Heritage 3D surveying and Modelling, Paestum, Italy (FBK organiser, MNIR participation)	http://www.fbk.eu/events/summer-school-cultural-heritage-3d-surveying-and-modeling
1 Sep 2014	Reshaping History, Rio de Janeiro, Brasil, (Invited speech, Roberto Scopigno, ISTI-CNR) "Interactive visual technologies for Digital Humanities"	http://emap.fgv.br/RHR-2014/
21-27 Sept 2014	Photogrammetry for Cultural Heritage Summer School, Romania (MNIR with FBK and the Centre for South-East European Studies, Romanian Academy)	https://www.facebook.com/pages/Photogrammetry-for-Cultural-Heritage-Summer-School/221908104679177?ref=hl http://www.mnir.ro/index.php/photogrammetry-applied-to-cultural-heritage-summer-school/
24-25 Sep 2014	AARG (Aerial Archaeology Research Group) 2014 Conference, Dublin (DISC, poster)	http://www.aarg2014.org/index.php/programme/abstracts/40-posters
26 Sep 2014	"Corner europeo:Taller La Arqueología en 3D". La noche de los investigadores en Jaén. European researcher's night. Comisión Europea, Horizonte 2020, Programme Marie Skłodowska-Curie. (Presentation, CAAI)	National Event https://lanochedelosinvestigadores.fundaciondescubre.es/jaen/

6-8 Oct 2014	12th EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage. Different Photogrammetric Approaches to 3D Survey of the Mausoleum of Romulus in Rome (presentation, CNR-ITABC)	http://diglib.eg.org/GCH2014
16 Oct 2014	University College Dublin seminar (DISC)	Masters students
17 Oct 2014	Trinity College Dublin seminar (DISC)	PhD students
17 Oct 2014	24th Rencontres CNRS Jeunes "Sciences et citoyens" Poitiers (Presentation, Archeotransfert)	National event http://www.cnrs.fr/sciencesetcitoyens/
22-23 Oct 2014	'Approaches to Archaeological Landscapes. Tools, methodology and case studies in the field of architectural and archaeological European Heritage', Bucharest (MNIR organiser, presentations MNIR and CISA)	https://cimec.files.wordpress.com/2014/10/lista_alfabetica_abstracturi_eng.pdf
30 Oct 2014	Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico. Paestum, XVII Edizione 29-30-31 october, 1 november 2014 (presentations CISA, CAAI, Discovery, Polimi)	http://www.borsaturismoarcheologico.it/
30 Oct 2014	Irish Earth Observation Symposium 2014, NUI Maynooth (DISC)	National event http://ieos2014.com/
3-5 Nov 2014	CHNT 2014, 19° Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies, Vienna, Austria (presentations Polimi, VisDim)	http://www.chnt.at/program-2014/
8 Nov 2014	EuroMed 2014, Limassol, Cyprus, (invited Keynote, Roberto Scopigno, ISTI-CNR) "Sampling and rendering high-fidelity 3D models for Cultural Heritage applications"	www.euromed2014.eu
17/11/14	European 'Reaching and Engaging Tourist Audiences with Digital Collections (Art Nouveau)'. Brussels (Participation: KMKG)	http://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/reaching-and-engaging-tourist-audiences-with-digital-collections-art-nouveau-17th-november-2014-tickets-13326083675
20 Nov 2014	Faculty of History, University of Bucharest – Non-invasive investigation used in archaeological research (Presentation, MNIR)	National event

25/11/14	TechItaly2014 "The Future of Cultural Heritage in Smart Cities", participation, Brussels (participation: KMKG)	http://www.techitaly.eu/index.php/cultural-heritage
28/11/14	Skane European Office conference, presentation, Brussels (participation: KMKG)	https://www.euagenda.eu/2014/11/28/Creative-Industries-Cultural-Heritage-Innovative-ways-of-capturi
8 Dec 2014	eCult Winter Stage, Athens (presentation, VisDim)	http://www.ecultobservatory.eu/events/ecult-winter-stage-athens-greece
9 Dec 2014	V-MusT Digital Museum Expo, Amsterdam (presentation, VisDim)	http://v-must.net/activities/digital-museum-expo-amsterdam
22 Jan 2015	Maison des Sciences de l'Homme d'Aquitaine, (MSHA) Bordeaux "Image 3D et SHS de la recherche a la valorisation" (Presentation, Archeotransfert)	National event http://www.msha.fr/msha/
6-7 Feb 2015	New Digital Technologies and Hungarian Innovations in Heritage Management – conference organized by the Hungarian National Academy of Science and the Central European University, Budapest (Presentation, CYI-STARC)	http://medievalstudies.ceu.edu/events/2015-02-06/new-digital-technologies-and-hungarian-innovations-in-heritage-management-%E2%80%93-archae
25-27 Feb 2015	6th International Workshop, 3D-ARCH'2015 3D Virtual Reconstruction and Visualization of Complex Architectures Avila, Spain "Low-cost surveys of the <i>Domus</i> of Stallius Eros in Pompeii" CISA	http://www.3d-arch.org/
30 Mar to 3 Apr 2015	CAA 2015 (presentations CETI, DISC and CISA, poster CISA)	http://caaconference.org/
25-6 Jun 2015	DPASSH (Digital Preservation for the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities)2015 Conference Dublin, Ireland (DISC, paper submitted)	http://dpassh.dri.ie/
2-5 Sep 2015	EAA conference (Digital Preservation for the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities)2015 Conference Glasgow, UK, (DISC session accepted awaiting paper selection)	http://eaaglasgow2015.com/session/3d-cultural-heritage-scientific-applications-and-communication-mediums/

Appendix 2: Publications

2012

D'Andrea, A., Niccolucci, F. and Fernie K., '*3D-ICONS: European project providing 3D models and related digital content to Europeana*', EVA Florence 2012.

D'Andrea, A., Niccolucci, F., Bassett, and Fernie, K., '*3D-ICONS: World Heritage Sites for Europeana: Making Complex 3D Models Available to Everyone*', VSMM 2012.

D'Andrea, A., '*Provenance e Paradata negli OpenData: il modello 3D-ICONS*', Opening the Past, Pisa, Italy, 14th-16th June 2013: http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/OP2013_pre_atti_rid.pdf

D'Andrea, A., '*Integrating Architectural and Archaeological 3D-Models into Europeana*', Newsletter di Archeologia CISA, Volume 3, 2012, pp. 87-109: http://www.unior.it/userfiles/workarea_231/Andrea%202012.pdf.

Ruiz, A. y Torres J. C. "Arqueología Virtual en Puente Tablas". *IV Congreso Internacional de Arqueología e Informática Gráfica*. Sociedad Española de Arqueología Virtual. Sevilla 20 a 22 June 2012.

2013

D'Andrea, A., Fernie, K., '*3D-Icons Metadata Schema for 3D Objects*', Newsletter di Archeologia CISA, Volume 4, 2013, pp. 159-181: online http://www.unior.it/userfiles/workarea_231/file/NL4/Articoli/03_DAndrea-Fernie.pdf.

D'Andrea, A., Fernie, K., '*CARARE 2.0: a metadata schema for 3D Cultural Objects*'. Digital Heritage 2013, International Congress, IEEE Proceedings. http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/content/download/3545/26919/file/87D%27Andrea_Fernie_digitalheritage2013.pdf

Callieri, M., Leoni, C., Dellepiane, M. and Scopigno, R., '*Artworks narrating a story: a modular framework for the integrated presentation of three-dimensional and textual contents*'. ACM WEB3D - 18th International Conference on 3D Web Technology, page 167-175 - June 2013. Online: http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/Publications/2013/CLDS13/web3D_cross.pdf

Dell'Unto, N., Ferdani, D., Leander, A., Dellepiane, M. and Lindgren, S., '*Digital reconstruction and visualization in archaeology Case-study drawn from the work of the Swedish Pompeii Project*'. Digital Heritage 2013 International Conference, page 621-628 - November 2013. Online: http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/Publications/2013/DFLDCL13/digitalheritage2013_Pompeii.pdf

Gonizzi Barsanti, S. and Guidi, G., "3D digitization of museum content within the 3DIcons project", ISPRS Ann. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., II-5/W1, pp. 151-156, 2013. Online: www.isprs-ann-photogramm-remote-sens-spatial-inf-sci.net/II-5-W1/151/2013/

Gonizzi Barsanti, S., Micoli, L.L., Guidi, G., "Quick textured mesh generation for massive 3D digitization of museum artifacts", 2013 Digital Heritage International Congress (DigitalHeritage), Vol. 1, pp. 197-201, IEEE, 2013. ISBN 978-1-4799-3169-9.

Guidi, G., Rodríguez Navarro, P., Micoli, L.L., Gonizzi Barsanti, S., Russo, M., "3D Digitizing a whole museum: a metadata centered workflow", 2013 Digital Heritage International Congress (DigitalHeritage), Vol. 2, pp. 307-310, IEEE, 2013. ISBN 978-1-4799-3169-9.

Guidi, G., Rodríguez Navarro, P., Gonizzi Barsanti, S., Loredana Micoli, L., Russo, M., "Quick textured mesh generation in Cultural Heritage digitization", Built Heritage 2013, Milan, Italy, 18-20 November 2013, pp. 877-882, [Selected for printed publication]. Online; http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/papers/bh2013_paper_324.pdf

Hermon, S., Bakirtzis, N., Kyriacou, P., "3D Documentation – Analysis - Interpretation"., "Digital libraries of 3D data – access and inter-operability"., " and The cycle of use and re-use of digital heritage assets"., Scientific Support for Growth & Jobs (2013): Cultural and Creative Industries, Brussels, Belgium., Session: posters and presentation. [24 Oct 2013].

Hermon, S., Ben-Ami, D., Khalaily, H., Avni, G., Iannone, G., Faka, M., (2013) "3D documentation of large-scale, complex archaeological sites: The Givati Parking excavation in Jerusalem"., Conference Proceedings, Digital Heritage 2013, Marseilles, France, vol 2, Session: Documentia. Digital Documentation of Archaeological Heritage, pp. 581

Hermon, S., Niccolucci, F., Yiakoupi, K., Kolosova, A., Iannone, G., Faka, M., Kyriacou, P., Niccolucci, V., (2013) "Documenting Architectonic Heritage in Conflict Areas. The case of Agia Marina Church, Derynia, Cyprus.", Conference Proceedings, Built Heritage 2013 Monitoring Conservation Management, Milan, Italy, 20 November, pp. 800 - 808. Available: http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/papers/bh2013_paper_216.pdf [20 Dec 2013].

Hermon, S., Khalaily, H., Avni, G., Reem, A., Iannone, G., Fakka, M., (2013) "Digitizing the Holy – 3D Documentation and analysis of the architectural history of the "Room of the Last Supper" – the Cenacle in Jerusalem"., Conference Proceedings, Digital Heritage 2013, Marseilles, France, vol 2, Session 3–Architecture, Landscape: Documentation & Visualization, pp. 359 - 362.

Jiménez Fernández-Palacios, b., Remondino, F., Lombardo, J., Stefani, C. and L. De Luca: "Web visualization of complex reality-based 3D models with Nubes". Digital Heritage 2013 Int. Congress, IEEE Proceedings.

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Martin-Beaumont N., Nony N., Deshayes B., Pierrot-Deseilligny M., De Luca L. Photographer-friendly workflows for image-based modelling of heritage artefacts. Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, XXIV International CIPA Symposium, Strasbourg, France, 2-6 September 2013.

Leoni, C., Callieri, M., Dellepiane, M. Rosselli Del Turco, R. and O'Donnell, D., *The Dream and the Cross: bringing 3D content in a digital edition*. Digital Heritage 2013 International Conference, page 281-288 - October 2013. pdf -> <http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/Publications/2013/LCDRO13/DreamAndTheCross.pdf>

Niccolucci, F., Felicetti, A., Amico, N. and D'Andrea, A., *Quality control in the production of 3D documentation of monuments*, Built Heritage 2013, proceedings: http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/papers/bh2013_paper_314.pdf

Remondino, F., Menna, F., Koutsoudis, A., Chamzas, C., El-Hakim, S., 2013: Design and implement a reality-based 3D digitisation and modelling project. Proc. IEEE Conference "Digital Heritage 2013", Vol. 1, pp. 137-144, 28 Oct - 1 Nov., Marseille, France. Published at: [10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2013.6743723](http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2013.6743723)

Ronzino, P., Niccolucci, F. and D'Andrea, A., *Built Heritage metadata schemas and the integration of architectural datasets using CIDOC-CRM*, Built Heritage 2013, proceedings, online: http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/papers/bh2013_paper_318.pdf

Ruiz, A. Sánchez, A, Martínez, A and Gómez, F. "El patrimonio arqueológico de los iberos en Europeana. Los proyectos CARARE y 3D-ICONS". Boletín de la ANABAD, LXIII (3): 343-356 <http://www.anabad.org/home/1-informacion-general/2286-ya-hemos-editado-el-boletin-anabad-no-3-de-2013.html>

Saleri R., Cappellini V., Nony N., Pierrot-Deseilligny M., Bardiere E., Campi M., De Luca L. UAV photogrammetry for archaeological survey: the Theaters area of Pompeii. 2013 Digital Heritage International Congress (DigitalHeritage), Vol. 2, IEEE (ISBN: 978-1-4799-3169-9).

Tolias, G., Avrithis Y. and Jeggou, H., 2013, *To aggregate or not to aggregate: selective match kernels for image search*, International Conference on Computer Vision (Oral), ICCV, Sydney, Australia, December 2013.

Varytimidis, C., Rapantzikos, K. and Kollias, S., 2013, *WaSH-ing visual repositories: searching Europeana using local features*, International conference on digital signal processing (DSP'13), Santorini, Greece, July 2013.

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